

Sound analysis based on phase information that connects time and frequency

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ABSTRACT

This paper intends to reveal some of the properties and possibilities for sound analysis combining the Fourier and Mellin transform. First, the general transforms are defined and it is introduced how these signal and spectrum representations relate to each other. Second, a central property of Mellin-based form of the Fourier transform; its affine scaling, which leads to the concept of a joined, logarithmic time/frequency-axis is introduced. Third, the concept of a time-frequency continuum that is perpendicular to the logarithmic time-frequency axis is introduced. Next is discussed how information guides itself through the time-frequency continuum and how components link and move together depending on their spectrum and signal characteristics. Finally, an attempt is made to connect the special features that characterize this analysis method to other signal analysis methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

The question of balancing between a time domain or frequency domain description is a fundamental issue in various areas like the design of band-limited oscillators, the description of wave-propagation, directional hearing, the modeling of excitation mechanisms, or the problem of sound source separation in general. Instead of focusing on one of these applications, this paper aims to reveal a general concept that direct this balancing. This is done by exploring the properties of a signal modeling concept intermediate to the Fourier and Mellin transform that puts the paradigm of time-frequency trade-off in a different perspective.

The Mellin transform essentially warps frequency content in conjunction with time. Its abstraction is generally promoted for its power to smoothly rescale and stretch either time or frequency content while preserving magnitude characteristics in the other domain. These elegant options are seen as accommodating abstractions for controlling our analysis, but they will not be the object of our investigations. What is often considered merely an intermediate form in the processing path to the Mellin abstraction; -the exponentially sampled signal and spectrum representations- are our real object of interest. In particular the intimate link of the exponential time representation with the exponentially sampled spectrum representation is

rarely recognized, but it will proof here to be a crucial element in time-frequency thinking. The practical implementation of exponential time/frequency sampling is is far from trivial.

2. FOURIER AND MELLIN TRANSFORM

In Fourier analysis it is possible to present a function in the time domain or the frequency domain and to convert a function in the time domain to the frequency domain and vice versa with help of the Fourier transform and it's inversion. The Fourier transform \mathcal{F} of a function $g(t)$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{F}\{g(t)\} = \hat{g}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t) e^{-i2\pi ft} dt \quad (1)$$

The Mellin transform \mathcal{M} of a function $g(x)$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{M}\{g(x)\} = \hat{g}(s) = \int_0^{\infty} g(x) x^{s-1} dx, \quad s \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2)$$

The Mellin transform is closely related to both the Laplace transform and the Fourier transform. Substitution of e^{-t} in (2) for the variable x gives the Laplace transform \mathcal{L} of the function $g(e^{-t})$:

$$\mathcal{L}\{g(e^{-t})\} = \hat{g}(s) = \int_0^{\infty} g(e^{-t}) e^{-st} dt \quad (3)$$

Since the Laplace transform can be seen as an extended form of the Fourier transform defined in (1), by substituting $i2\pi f$ for the variable s in (2) the Fourier transform of $g(e^{-t})$ is derived:

$$\mathcal{F}\{g(e^{-t})\} = \hat{g}(f) = \int_0^{\infty} g(e^{-t}) e^{-i2\pi ft} dt \quad (4)$$

The Laplace transform and the Fourier transform that are derived from the Mellin transform are now both defined as an unilateral or one-sided transformation. Both transforms can also be defined as a bilateral or two-sided transformation by extending the limits of integration to all real numbers.

The relation between the Mellin transform and the Fourier transform can be written symbolically as:

$$\mathcal{M}\{g(x)\}_{s=i2\pi f} = \mathcal{F}\{g(e^{-t})\}_f \quad (5)$$

It is from these definitions that the Mellin transform can be interpreted as the Fourier transform of an exponentially warped time signal or as a logarithmic-time Fourier transform [1]

3. TIME AND FREQUENCY SAMPLING

The definitions and relations between the integral transforms from the previous section doesn't take into account any later sampling of the variables. The variable f for which the transformed functional result $\hat{g}(f)$ is specified in (4) only specifies a frequency dependent result, where it does not matter if its plotted along a linear or an exponential frequency scale. The same frequency variable f reappears in the complex exponent $e^{-i2\pi ft}$ where it is scaled with the time variable t . The correlation between time and frequency that this integral transform is representing, is powered by the parallel development of frequency f and time t information in this complex exponent. [Note that the product of time and frequency is caught in the imaginary part of the complex exponent and in reality is expressing a phase angle. So, the integral actually sums phase differences, that are disguised as a sum of products.]

This leads to an ambiguity. Consider a sine signal with a frequency that changes logarithmically with linear time. When evaluated on an exponential time-scale, this signal will show a constant product of time and frequency tf in the complex exponent. Alternatively, a sine signal now with a linear frequency dependence on linear time, will in exponential time have an exponential frequency increment. If the frequency variable f is also allowed to have the same exponential increment, this will again lead to a constant product ft in the exponent. So, the formulation in (5) expresses a final result on a frequency scale, indifferent if the frequency term in the integral proceeds linear or exponentially. Apart from this ambiguity, the Mellin integral also implies that a change in time offset in relation to the starting frequency will largely change the outcome of the integral and thus also the observed frequency content.

3.1 Two forms for the Mellin integral

The correspondence between the Mellin integral and the Fourier integral seen in (5) lead to the expression of the transformed result as a function $\hat{g}(f)$ based in the frequency domain. This frequency domain function holds a spectrum representation, but one that is not necessarily comparable to the spectrum of the signal on a linear frequency axis. The general formulation of the Mellin integral seen in (2) offers some powerful abstractions in formulating derivatives of time functions. However in (4), these properties account for the magnitude information only, but do not apply to the phase/frequency information as this information is caught in the imaginary part of the complex exponent and is thus evaluated as the product $-ft$ against linear time. For true frequency derivatives that are comparable to those of the general Fourier representation, but with some of the Mellin properties, it is necessary to evaluate the exponentially sampled time function $g(e^t)$ against exponentially progressing time e^t and exponentially decaying frequency e^{-f} variables.

$$\hat{g}(e^f) = \int_0^\infty g(e^t) e^{i2\pi e^{(t-f)}} e^t dt \quad (6)$$

Formula (6) describes a convolution with an exponentially frequency sweeping complex exponential. As only the imag-

inary part is involved and magnitude remains the same, this convolution process is thus comparable to an all-pass filtering. Apart from an offset, a sine wave with an exponentially changing instantaneous frequency over time $f_i = e^t$, is essentially identical to a sine wave with an exponentially changing instantaneous phase $\phi_t = e^t$ as a function of time. If now the instantaneous phase ϕ_t as it is expressed in the time domain is taken as the reference for the time variable, the dependency is reversed and thus $t = \ln(\phi_t)$.

Moreover, a sine wave with a constant frequency f can be observed over exponentially sampled time. If this frequency is taken to be the constant factor, whatever the moment in time, than still the amount of phase distance travelled at the sampling points will increase exponentially. The logarithm $\ln(\phi_f)$ of the series of phase ϕ_f observations will show a constant increase, that is directly proportional to the frequency f of the sine wave, so $f = \ln(\phi_t)$. This changes formula (6) into

$$\hat{g}(\phi_f) = \int_0^\infty g(\phi_t) e^{i2\pi e^{(\ln \phi_t - \ln \phi_f)}} e^t dt \quad (7)$$

Note that a phase change over time is still frequency, and a phase change with constant frequency still denotes time, but time and frequency are now allowed to vary in relation to each other. Hence, the exponential time and frequency scaling from the Mellin integral can still be maintained, without the problematic effect that a shift in time will change the frequency content. Furthermore, by linking the exponential dependency exclusively to the phase, only the imaginary part of the complex exponent is warped. Thus, for the real part of the complex exponent that describes the amplitude, the exponential behavior is no longer implicitly linked to exponential time or exponential frequency. A dependency on exponential time is essentially a logarithmic dependency as the typical natural preset is that amplitude changes exponentially with linear time or with linear frequency. The modified transformation in (6) will thus have properties of all the general integral transforms that were defined in the previous section. It will have a property of the Mellin transform for any information that links to an exponential change in phase, have a property of the Fourier transform for the frequency and it will have a property of the Laplace transform for any amplitude information that varies exponentially with linear time or linear frequency. Under these modified conditions the Fourier transform still works as normal, but the derivatives of a phase change against time, will now no longer include an amplitude term as this was contained in the real part of the integral. The ability to derive on frequency without a gain change may seem an undesirable concept if ones intention is to evaluate or to process frequency content on base of amplitude, but the ability to still evaluate or process frequency content without changing the amplitude could prove to be a valuable option.

4. EXPONENTIAL SAMPLING AND THE MELLIN DOMAIN

An exponentially re-sampled time signal is the starting point for either one of the two flavours (4) or (6) of the Mellin

Figure 1. Signals in the time domain (left), related exponentially sampled series (middle) and connected linear frequency spectra (right).

transform. The two forms clearly separate when the spectrum content is to be considered. Formulation (6) essentially converts a logarithmic time representation to a logarithmic frequency representation, where both representations will appear to exist in one and the same exponentially sampled domain (see Figure 1, middle column). The familiar relationships that exist between the time domain and the frequency domain are invariable mathematical properties, but their interpretation is inseparable from the linear increment by which the information is distributed on either the time axis or the frequency axis. The exponential sampling followed by a presentation as a linear sequence gives the time axis a logarithmic interpretation. That the original linear association between the data points now proceeds on this proportional scale can however not be read from its now linear sequential storage. A Fast Fourier transform (FFT) procedure does not check for the original clock count and just assumes its time or frequency proceeding linearly. As a result, the FFT result of any such linear stored series, that before had the association of a logarithmic time signal representation, will lead to what in linear FFT terms is considered a frequency domain representation comparable to the Mellin formulation (4). This spectrum is not the logarithmic frequency spectrum of the logarithmic time signal as in (6).

This Mellin spectrum representation is comparable to a Mel-frequency cepstrum representation, as it is the linear Fourier transform of information that is logarithmically distributed along the dependent axis. This representation will be referred to as the Exponential Sweep Spectrum [ESS]. As mentioned before, the exponential sampling converts any narrow frequency band signal, i.e. a sine wave, to a regular exponential sweep [EST] (see Figure 1). On the other hand, the exponential sampling of a signal with a wide frequency band, i.e. a pulse [TP], will remain a pulse [EP] on the logarithmic-time axis. Both the exponential sweep [EST], and the pulse [EP] have the same magnitude distribution in the ESS, they only differ in their ESS-phase representation. The convolution of an exponential sweep with an identical, but time reversed exponential sweep [ESF] will convert the exponential sweep [EST] to a pulse [EP] in the exponentially sampled domain. This conversion, that complies to the convolution described in (6), is actually comparable to a linear scale Fourier analysis, as all constant frequency information is summed into one component with an offset on the axis that now has the identity of frequency.

What is valid for a single parallel sweep is also valid for a sum of parallel sweeps. This property of the formulation (6) which is called in general the superposition principle can symbolically written as:

$$\mathcal{F}(s_1 + s_2) \longrightarrow \mathcal{F}(s_1) + \mathcal{F}(s_2) \quad (8)$$

Aside the superposition principle, the homogeneity principle is also valid. The homogeneity principle can symboli-

cally written as:

$$as \longrightarrow a\mathcal{F}(s) \quad (9)$$

Due to the linearity of the Mellin transform [2], the convolution of any sum of shifted exponential sinusoid sweeps with the same basic time reversed exponential sweep that functions as a kernel [ESF] will pile up all exponentially warped sinusoids according to their own frequency offset.

The convolution of an exponentially sampled signal with this time reversed exponential sweep kernel is the actual implementation of the transform (6). Note that a sine wave with a low frequency will, after its exponentially resampling, reach the fastest movement later, and thus reappear as an exponential sweep that is more displaced to the right on the frequency axis. As a result the spectrum has an opposite directed logarithmic frequency ordering. To be consistent, also in Figure 1 the exponential sampling from the linear frequency axis is done from right to left and the result is that the direction of the corresponding linear frequency axis is reversed. The pulse [EP] in the exponentially sampled domain can thus have two interpretations, that of an exponentially sampled pulse in the time domain or that of a single frequency band on an exponentially sampled frequency axis. The convolution with the reversed sweep [ESF] will bring any logarithmically sampled time signal to its spectrum on a logarithmic frequency axis, while the product of the convolution with the forward version [ESP] of the same sweep will bring any spectrum with a logarithmic frequency axis to its logarithmically sampled time signal. When staying in this exponentially sampled domain, this implementation of the transform thus has an inverse. The sweep [ESF] and its inverse [EST] both have an ESS with a flat magnitude characteristic. Both versions of the sweep can be seen as impulse responses of all-pass filters, with their convolution and deconvolution properties characterized by the opposite polarity of the phase in the ESS.

Moreover, also the exponentially sampled impulse series [EGT] and the exponentially sampled harmonic series [EGF] comprise essentially the same shape, only time reversed. As a result, both have identical ESS magnitude characteristics, and phase curves with opposite polarities. This implies that any convolution that is applied along this joint scale, using either one of the geometric series [EGT] or [EGF] as an impulse response, will be a magnitude pattern selection process (filtering) that searches periodicity in both the time domain and the frequency domain at the same time. This unifies the principle of periodicity detection over both domains.

5. A JOINED TIME-FREQUENCY AXIS

The relationship between time and frequency, $T = 1/f$, is in the Fourier representation generally associated with independent, perpendicular axes. The exponential sampling straightens out the $1/x$ curve and parallels the logarithmic time and logarithmic frequency axes. This parallelism means that also other reciprocal relationships between time and frequency that exist as a Fourier pair unify. An

example of such a proportion is the length of the analysis window in the time domain that curtails the bandwidth in the frequency domain. This proportion becomes a linear distance on a shared logarithmic axis. The benefit of the definition of both the analysis window and the bandwidth on the same axis is that no longer the incommensurable relation between time and frequency will be a preset in the analysis, as it can be optimized by widening in either the time or frequency perspective. With the exponentially sampled domain, the notions of zero time and zero frequency are missing. Both time and frequency values can still be measured in an absolute sense, but their zeroes are never reached due to the logarithmic approach. When there are no scale zeroes to measure against, a transformation becomes affine, which means that the order along the scale is preserved by maintaining a fixed time-frequency product. This specific property turns up as an extra constraint that directs the exponential time sampling process. With progressively larger sampling periods (downsampling), something has to give in at the Nyquist frequency end. This means that, for a practical implementation, during the exponential re-sampling process the frequency range needs to be progressively band-limited. So, any signal that appears on the time entry point on the logarithmic time axis will at that moment be sampled at an extreme high rate and thus be spectrally rich and full of high frequency details. Note that this entry point behaves like a sort of zero scale mark as it connects the logarithmic time scale to a physical instant that exists in linear time. Over time the waveform squeezes by the downsampling while it at the same time loses high frequency detail by the progressive band-limiting. The signal will be muted when the lowest frequency components from the complex reach their Nyquist limit.

6. THE TIME-FREQUENCY CONTINUUM

As mentioned before, the joint time-frequency axis is a dual representation where the logarithmic time and the logarithmic frequency share the same axis. Despite this association, the notions of time domain and frequency domain remain to exist. The two identities are however not anymore that strictly incongruent as with the ordinary square-matrix of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). As an extra, the convolution process that brings the signal from its time identity to its spectrum identity can be sectioned. This is realized by using cascaded all-pass filters with impulse responses that each sweep over the full frequency range, but in a fraction of the time. For the inverse transform, the impulse responses are reversed.

This allows a fluent transformation from one to the other domain identity, with intermediate representations that are neither a pure time domain nor a pure frequency domain description. These intermediate representations can be seen as descriptions where frequency changes with constant time, or where time sampling changes with constant frequency. Note that it is possible to pass over the invariant-frequency or invariant-time horizontal by overdoing with an extra filter section.

Figure 2. Magnitude distribution over the time-frequency-continuum for a sine wave. The black arrow indicates the exponential sampling direction and entry point for the signal. The red curve at this intersection shows the logarithmic signal magnitude (envelope) along a logarithmic time axis. The grey arrow marks the exponential sampling direction and entry point when starting from the linear spectrum. The red curve at this intersection shows now the logarithmic spectrum magnitude that at this vertical level has a logarithmic frequency axis interpretation.

Figure 3 demonstrates how an exponentially sampled sine wave travels top-down through the time-frequency continuum and thereby integrates to become its own narrow spectral peak representation. At the stages in between it can not be said that its frequency or time information, simply because both orderings only exist by their constant sampling along the axis. If the incoming sinusoid would have had an increasing frequency already on the linear time scale, then after the exponential sampling its resulting sweep would have increased faster and the point of focus would have been reached at an earlier stage in the continuum. So, the intermediate horizontal intersections have the interpretation of lines with constant acceleration or deceleration of phase against time, or the other way around.

6.1 First derivatives

Any signal component with constant frequency that is exponentially re-sampled over the time line, will have an exponential increasing instantaneous frequency (see EST in Figure 1). This constant component behaves as a linear offset in the exponent that denotes the center frequency offset along the scale.

Taking the derivative against linear time will isolate the frequency as a constant component. This derivative, called the instantaneous frequency (IF), guides a tangent that linearly turns along the logarithmic time axis at the top. The turning is linear because time and frequency share the same

Figure 3. Magnitude distribution over the time-frequency-continuum for a pulse.

Figure 4. Magnitude distribution over the time-frequency-continuum for a periodic pulse series.

exponential proportion. Note how in all time-frequency continuum plots (see figure 2, 3 and 4), beams or rays show up that, according to this IF-tangent, all focus on designated spots along the logarithmic frequency axis. For all the samples along the logarithmic time axis, the proportional phase change over time (the frequency) is constant, or in other words, the focusing point along the frequency axis marks where all information along the time axis that has a constant time frequency product integrates on.

Aside the derivative against time of the complex valued time function, there is also a derivative against frequency for the complex valued spectrum function. This derivative represents the group delay (GD). A pulse in time will have a flat spectrum with a phase spectrum that has a linear increasing term that describes the time-offset of the pulse. After exponential sampling along the frequency axis this first linear-phase term changes to an exponentially sweeping phase function (see Figure 1, ESF derived from FP). The derivative of this function against frequency isolates this linear offset as a constant factor that represents the group delay. This means, that all information along the frequency axis that is phase locked on the same point in time (and thus has the same group delay) will show beams

or rays that now focus upward on this specific spot on the time axis (see Figure 3).

6.2 Binding factors

Both differentials, the IF and the GD, direct how the information as being either a time or frequency component, will focus within the time-frequency continuum. The property that the grouped components share in time or in frequency, is a constant fixed product of time and frequency, actually a fixed product of a time period and frequency distance. The same product appears in the complex exponential as $e^{i\pi tf}$ with either the signal or spectral description.

Note that the phase information, seen as a function of time or seen as a function of frequency, has in its absolute sense no further relevance as to precisely carry the differential (IF or GD) which codes the actual information how to focus in the time-frequency continuum.

6.3 Sharpness / resolution

The sharpness of the spectral peak at the point where all time information concentrates on the frequency axis (its bandwidth) is not determined by the frequency resolution entailed in the analysis procedure (the all-pass filter impulse response or the Mellin that convolves the signal to its spectrum), but by the actual width or length of its exposure over the logarithmic time line.

6.4 Second and higher order derivatives

As described in a section above, the derivate along the time axis known as instantaneous frequency (IF) and derivative along the frequency axis known as group delay (GD) both indicate how the information in either representation will focus on the other axis, or at an intermediate point within the time-frequency continuum. Information groups together along either axis on base of a shared linear IF or GD component or shared tf product. A constant linear increasing first derivative means a constant second derivative. Thus a flat second derivative along the time axis (DIF) or a flat second derivative along the frequency axis (DGD) indicates that successive information will focus at some point in the time-frequency continuum. When a first constant second derivative switches to a different offset than this marks the appearance of new information in the time-frequency continuum. A zero DIF or DGD would mean a lack of directivity to focus. Information that has a fixed, frequency counterbalanced phase difference along the frequency axis, or information that is spread over the time axis and shares a fixed frequency response, will always have a flat second derivative on its exposure along the axis. Grouping in either time or frequency means sharing the same offset pattern for the second derivative. This means that higher order derivatives will report on exclusive binding of different component groups over the continuum. For this to work, the grouped components need not to be sequentially ordered. Contributing to the same second derivative indicates mutual binding on base of correlation, while binding to a differently grouped second derivative can be interpreted as independency.

7. RANDOMNESS IN TIME AND FREQUENCY

Having a predominantly flat DIF means having only correlated components over time, and as a result only sharp peaks in the frequency distribution. Having a predominantly flat DGD means having only correlated components over frequency that in essence relate to sharp pulses in the time signal. Randomness can be defined as a zero prone DIF and zero prone DGD, which implies that both amplitude distributions in time or frequency have, on the average, not the tendency nor the mass/width to curve according to an e^{-t^2/σ^2} or e^{-f^2/σ^2} shape, thus no Gaussian trends in either domain. The result is that there is no preference value in either time or frequency that could lead to a centered value around a mean (see Figure 5). Peaked or pulsed information may still appear along either the time or frequency axis in the form of uniform randomly distributed spikes or uniform randomly distributed sinusoids. If the sharpness of information is not associated with a certain combined appearance of a correlation over a certain distance away from its focusing point, than there is randomness (see Figure 6). Note that a signal could be synthesized where there is focusing and thus correlation only in the middle between the pure time and frequency descriptions. It would be hard to characterize such a signal by using general signal and spectrum analysis methods that can not explore the options between these domains. One implication is that it is impossible to pinpoint randomness and thus noise by a single spectral or time domain description only. A specification of randomness must at least be a spectra-temporal description.

7.1 Gaussian properties and exponential sampling

When a Gaussian distributed data set is exponentially sampled along its dependent axis, than as a result the former e^{-x^2/σ^2} shaped distribution will, now on the logarithmically scaled dependent axis, change to a parabolic shaped distribution with a bending scaled by $-x^2/\sigma^2$. By calculating the second derivative, this second order (quadratic) factor can be isolated as a constant. A distribution can thus be tested on its non-Gaussianity by testing the average deviance from this second order parabolic model. This non-Gaussianity criterion, is an important binding factor in blind source separation techniques [3] [4]. This criterion complies closely with the earlier described criteria for independency as a grouped difference or deviance from a constant second derivative seen with the DIF or DGD. The Mellin transform is one-sided and for its operation it needs a complex valued signal at its input. This complex valued signal can be obtained for example by the Hilbert transform of a real valued signal. In contrast to a real valued signal that is ideally distributed around a zero mean, the now complex signal amplitude values distribute around an all-positive mean, which suits the affine property of the transform. Testing for non-Gaussianity using a Mellin-like transform has the advantage that also the third order term, called the skewness, is able to contribute and that not only the fourth order term, called the kurtosis, has to be used for deviance weighting and grouping. Furthermore, with

Figure 5. Magnitude distribution over the time-frequency-continuum for pink noise.

the DIF or DGD approach, frequency can be used as an offset and thus there are no requirements to precisely assess the mean, neither is there a need for having at least one Gaussian distributed component in a mix before any contrasting independent component can be isolated.

8. SHIFTING INFORMATION IN THE TIME-FREQUENCY CONTINUUM

Sifting information in the TF-continuum The reason why a peak is able to stand out in the time/frequency continuum, is because somewhere higher up, over some wider region the phase curve showed a progression that matched to an exponential incrementing phase curve template. The sharpness or focussing of a magnitude peak over some width, is just an acknowledgement of the consistent grouping of information that is linked along the axis. As amplitude is preserved all over the continuum, we could choose to subtract this information at any point where it maximally peaks along the time axis, or any point along the frequency axis, or in between, while having in mind that this will be the point with least effects on other identities in the continuum. Just one isolated spectral peak can be reverse transformed to its related time signal representation. This signal can again be used as a phase as a function of time template, a kernel to cross-correlate all other signal information with and that will produce a maximum spectral focusing for all signal components that have a comparable frequency development with time. Here it is the specificity of the time progression of the template, the deviance from the normal, that determines the amount of focusing or isolation for all other information that is linked to it. As the normal linear progression of phase with time is non specific, as this is just frequency, the quadratic progression of phase with time will be the carrier, where again the higher powers/derivatives (the ones that specify the non-Gaussianity) determine the amount of success or independence. Note the generality of the procedure, as one isolated peak on the time axis can be a template to isolate a spectral phase template that can be used to select all frequency information

that has a comparable time development.

9. CONCLUSIONS

Due to the properties of the Mellin transform, the Fourier transform was reformulated to a transform from phase as a function of logarithmic time to phase as a function of logarithmic frequency. Phase is used as a binding factor that connects both domains as it is basically the same reference point in both domains. Due to the one-sidedness of the transform, domain circularity is no longer a feature of the transformation. Events may occur in the exponentially sampled time domain, or spectrum components may appear in the exponentially sampled frequency domain, without any preconditioned necessity for a (periodic) reappearance. The objective of searching for a fundamental periodicity can thus be replaced by a stronger, more flexible concept, that of a search for repetition, which may even be a one-time event only. With a sign directed integral, past and future will keep their annotation and also the notion of phase is no longer ambiguous as rotational direction remains preserved. A general Fourier description would offer the same options when applied one-sided, but it is the exponential warped scale that gives this integration the option to deal with time-variability also. The exponentially warped phase domain offers a linearization of time and frequency dependencies and presents a method to resolve grouped components in a time-frequency continuum based on their characteristic match to a second order dependency.

10. REFERENCES

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